

A Correlational Perspective of Social Media-Related Behaviours and Students' Discipline in Public Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The study examined Social media-related behaviours and students' discipline in public secondary schools in Kogi State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to investigate how often students interact with social media and the effect of this on students' discipline. Descriptive research of the survey type was used for the study. The population consisted of all the 55,800 students in all the public secondary schools in Kogi State. The sample for the study consisted of 900 students, 500 teachers and 45 schools. The samples were selected using proportionate sampling and simple random sampling techniques. Two self-designed

instruments were used to collect relevant data. They are; Students' Discipline Questionnaire (SDQ) for teachers and Students' Social Media-Related Behaviour Questionnaire (SSMRBQ) for students. The validity of the instruments was ascertained by experts in the area of educational management and test and measurement. The reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained for SDQ for teachers and 0.88 for SSMRBQ for students. The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. All the hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that most of the students were engaged in social media. A high percentage of the students (81.2%) in the study area often interact with social media. The study showed that there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline. The study further revealed that there was a significant relationship in the social media-related behaviours and student's discipline in the rural areas. Based on the findings, it was recommended that school administrators and teachers needed to inform and educate students on the harmful effects and the negative behaviours that students pick up from social media on regular bases.

Key words: Social media related behaviour, Student discipline, Rural areas, Secondary schools.

Introduction

Social network sites which were introduced in less than two decades ago have drawn large numbers of students' users. Kord (2008) confirmed that the involvement of students in social media has increased considerably. Recent studies carried out by some researchers reported that 60% to 70% of students in secondary schools are actively involved with at least a particular social media (Tüfekci, 2008). In buttressing this report, Singh and Gill (2015) revealed that 70.1% of students spent almost an hour daily on social media. Stainbank and Gurr (2016) also submitted that up to 52.3% of the students visited social media sites 1-4 times daily and that 40% of them accessed social media more than five times in a day. Furthermore, Fasae and Adegbilero-Iwar

(2016) revealed that 70% of respondents used social media daily and that students' visits to social media sites were for entertainment and communication rather than learning. Boyd (2008) reported that teenagers and students embrace social media to interact with peers, play games and chat. Students can spend several hours attending to different social media sites even during formal classes and library sessions thereby creating distractions and reducing the time for focusing on their studies.

In Kogi State, the majority of the public secondary schools are located in urban areas because of the teeming population of secondary school students in the urban areas. Out of the 241 public secondary schools in the state, 160 are located in the urban areas while 81 public secondary schools are located in rural areas. The major areas in Kogi State include Lokoja, the state capital, Koton-Karfe, Okene, Kabba, Idah, Dekina, Anpka, Egbe, Isanlu and Odo-Ere. Students located in these urban areas have greater access to internet; hence, they were more involved with social media. Furthermore, majority of the public secondary schools in Kogi State are co-educational. Out of the 241 public secondary schools in the state only three are exclusively for girls, and only two are exclusively for boys.

Our experience and observations have shown that students skip the time for studies and engage in long hours of social networking; this, in turn, may be affecting them in various ways. Many students seem to prefer being on social media site to reading their books. Students were often observed during school time in the various hidden places either discussing social networks or browsing with their phone. Onasanya (2002) was of the view that many young people are addicted to social networking activities, abandoning homework and reading time in preference to chatting with friends. Even at lecture time, it appears many students are on phones engaging in one form of chatting or the other which can be quite distracting and lead to loss of concentration.

Students in Kogi state appear to put up various anti-social behaviours, which may be the result of being exposed to social media. Sleeping in the classroom especially during lessons could be a result of staying late into the night on social networks. Coming late to school especially on a regular basis could also be the result of staying late into the night on social networks. It is very common these days to hear students using foul languages and at times uttering statements that are repugnant to common sense. The problem of indecent dressing that appears to engulf the nation today cannot be divorced from the influences that students and youths generally copy from the social media. Poor time management due to long hours of social networking, cyberbullying,

addiction and exposure to pornographic and other unwholesome materials appear to be some of the social media-related negative behaviours which students exhibit because of their usage of the social media.

Ajelabi (2005) asserted that internet chatting is widely utilised by secondary school students both male and female in Nigeria. Some researchers found out that gender interests differ in social networking activities. Boyd (2008) female students are more likely to use social networking sites than their male counterpart. For girls, social networking sites are places to reinforce pre-existing friendships while for boys who use the sites, the networks provide opportunities for flirting and making new friends. Kan (2010) was of the view that quite some male students use social networking sites for knowledge more than their female counterparts. His findings, on the contrary, showed that students are addicted to social networking regardless of their sex. He further found out that addiction tends to take students' time and keep them from engaging in other activities.

Discipline and indiscipline are two sides of a coin. Discipline could be referred to as a manifestation of positive behaviour that is geared towards obedience and willingness to abide by rules of the society. Ajayi (2019) defined students' discipline as orderly conduct of an individual which is gained through training in self-control and in habits of obedience to socially approved standard of thoughts and actions. On the other hand, indiscipline is a behavioural disorder which is classified as an act of delinquency. Ugurhu et al. (2015) revealed that teachers perceived disciplined students as those who obey school rules, and furthermore they also perceived behaviours not acceptable within the society as unwanted behaviour in the school environment.

Kulbir (2011) defined discipline in school as respect for school laws and regulations and the maintenance of an established standard of behaviour and implies self-control, restraints, respect for oneself and others. A behaviour that contradicts the above becomes indiscipline. According to Tunor (2002), if students cultivate the habit of discipline in schools, there will be smooth running of the school system, but the reverse will be the case if students are not disciplined. Ehiane (2014) concluded that school rules and regulations are important in moulding the character of students. Kulbir (2011) identified various forms of indiscipline among secondary students such as truancy, lateness to school, cultism, drug abuse, stealing and many other anti-social behaviours. He noted that many of the acts of indiscipline are directed against constituted authorities and established rules. Discipline is an essential ingredient of peace, harmony and progress of any society. From

the above, we, therefore, argue that lack of discipline will make a society to be prone to social vices such as corruption, stealing and armed robbery, vandalism, cultism, prostitution, examination malpractices, dishonesty, disobedience to civil rules, ethnic and religious crises, and drug trafficking among others. Enose (2010) in his study revealed that a wide range of strategies are used in managing student's behavioural problems in schools (such as expulsion, suspension, physical punishment, detention, reprimanding, kneeling, guidance and counselling, rewards, and others).

From these, one could argue that the success of the school system depends on the level of discipline of staff and students. A school characterised by high level of indiscipline will find it difficult to achieve its aims and objectives. It is the responsibility of the school head to maintain discipline in the school. However, he cannot do this alone; he has to involve the Assistant Principal, Heads of Departments, members of staff, prefects and the students. One of the cardinal objectives of education, as spelt out in the revised National Policy on Education (2013), is to inculcate the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society. To achieve this in our secondary schools, the concept of discipline must not be taken for granted.

Social networking sites had brought both good and bad influence on the present generation. Social networking sites have helped students to acquire knowledge from one another over the internet without necessarily having to meet physically. On the other hand, social networking sites have caused many problems. The rate at which students pick up behaviours and habits on social media whether such behaviours and habits are good or bad is alarming. Our experiences as teacher and lecturer showed that social media stands as a major challenge to students' discipline in schools. For instance, many students have lost interest in their studies as they spend most of their time on these sites. Even the youths, in general, use social networking sites as a means of interaction, socialising and for entertainment purposes.

Social networking sites harbour many unsafe elements, and many people are concerned about some major problems that go along with it, which include poor academic performance and behavioural changes. Banquil and Chua (2009) came up with the conclusion that social networking sites do affect students' academic performance adversely. It directly affects a student's behaviour if the student invests his time in social networking sites instead of his studies. Badri and Al-Rashedi (2017) revealed that in the process of using social networking if students encounter any negative thing, it would affect their performance negatively. Paul (2012), in his research on effects of online

social networking on students behavioural changes found that there is statistically significant relationship between time spent by students on online social networks and their academic performance. On the other hand, Tüfekci, (2008) argued that students often use social networking sites to discuss their academic issues formally and also to interact with their instructors, teachers and Professors, therefore does not have negative effect on them. This was in reverse as observed in the study area.

The above contradictions indicate that some of the postings on social networking sites are informative and educative while some are nothing but distractions to students. Some secondary school students have formed the habit of visiting different social networking sites that it has started influencing their attitude; academically, physically and socially. However, the introduction of social media technologies to the public, such as email and chat rooms have generated a lot of contradictions and arguments among scholars. Some authors opined that these forms of technology would negatively impact on students' social lives and reduce their level of discipline (Ekpo, 2007; Badri and Al-Rashedi, 2017). Jaffar, Mohammed and Shahor (2019) found out that the use of social media in Pakistan has more negative influence on a student's behaviour than the positive aspect. According to Clement (2017) on penetration of leading social networks in Nigeria as at third quarter of 2017, 41% of Nigeria population were on Facebook, 41% on WhatsApp, 25% on Instagram, 25% on YouTube, and 24% on Facebook messenger.

Ekpo (2007) observed that students most times, abuse the use of these very socialising tools by neglecting the informative and educative benefits they offer. The neglect of educational benefits has endangered students in becoming victims of sexual predators, cyberbullying and harassment, posting or downloading of inappropriate pictures and other materials. This could affect students negatively in their reading habits, academics and social life due to the amount of time dedicated to the social world. Badri and Al-Rashedi A. (2017) revealed that in the process of using social networking if students encounter any negative thing, it would affect their performance negatively.

Statement of the Problem

Social media has become the mainstream communication method for many people since its inception. In particular, students in high schools have adopted these forms of communication as an avenue to keep in touch with family and friends. Students spend a considerable time on social media, thereby getting exposed to social media-related problems such as addiction and negligence of duties. This poses a great challenge to students' discipline in schools because influences and

habits that are as a result of students' exposure to social media have lots of impact on students' behaviours. The fact is that whatever students see or hear on social media, they will want to practice. Cases of insubordination and female students absconding from home to meet their social media lovers abound in society. Enose (2010) confirmed that the involvement of students in social media had increased considerably since 2004.

Hence, the internet has become a virtual meeting place where adolescent students hang out with their peers to pass time. Extended presence on social networking sites appears to have harmful effects on the level of students' discipline. Poor time management is a grave act of indiscipline that can be exhibited by anybody. Long hours spent on social networking sites seem to increase the chances of students picking up negative influences and habits. Therefore, this study sought to investigate social media-related behaviours and its influence on students' discipline in public secondary schools in Kogi State.

Research Questions

1. How often do students interact with social media in Kogi state public secondary schools?
2. What is the level of students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools.
2. There is no significant relationship in the social media-related behaviours and students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools, situated in rural areas.

Research Method

The descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted for the study. Descriptive design is appropriate for the study because it involved the collection of data to describe the prevailing characteristics as they exist regarding social media-related behaviour and students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools. The population of the study consisted of all the 55,800 students in all the 241 public secondary schools in Kogi State. The population of the teachers in the state as at the time of this study was 2,835. A sample of 900 students and 500 teachers were drawn from 45 public secondary schools using proportionate simple random sampling technique. The instruments used for the study were two self-designed questionnaires tagged Students' Discipline Questionnaire (SDQ) for teachers and Students' Social Media-Related Behaviour Questionnaire (SSMRBQ) for students. The instruments were validated by lecturers in Educational

Management and Tests, Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instruments was ensured using test-retest method. The reliability coefficient of 0.86 and 0.88 was obtained for the instruments respectively. The instruments were personally administered by the researcher with the aid of two research assistants. Data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics that were used include frequency count and percentages. The inferential statistics that were used include Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). All the hypotheses generated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussions

Research question 1: How often do students interact with social media in Kogi state public secondary schools? The result was presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Students interaction with Social Media

S/N	Items	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Comment
1	How frequently do you visit social networking sites per day?	Once	169	18.8	Low
		Twice	389	43.2	Moderate
		More than twice	333	37.0	Low
		Never	9	1.0	Low
2	How many minutes do you spend on social networking sites on each visit?	Less than 5 minutes	27	3.0	Low
		5 minutes	99	11.0	Low
		10 minutes	363	40.3	Moderate
		More than 10 minutes	411	45.7	Moderate
3	Do you respond to information alerts from social networking sites while in class	Yes	244	27.1	Low
		No	656	72.9	High
4	How many social networking sites are you currently a member of?	1	124	13.8	Low
		2	487	54.1	Moderate
		3	201	22.3	Low
		More than 3	88	9.8	Low

Table 1 revealed students' interaction with social media. It was revealed that 169 (18.8%) of the respondents visited social media sites once per day. Up to 389 (43.2%) of the respondents visited it twice per day. As much as 333 (37.0%) visited social media sites more than twice per day, while 9 (1.0%) of the total respondents had never visited social media sites. This implies that almost all the students visited social media sites every day, either while at school or at home. The

findings also revealed the minutes that the students spend on social networking sites per visit. it was revealed that 27 respondents (3.0%) spent less than 5 minutes, 99 (11.0%) spent 5 minutes, and 363 (40.3%) spent 10 minutes. Up to 411 (45.7%) spent more than 10 minutes on social networking sites. The result according to students' response to information alerts from social networking sites while in class revealed that majority (72.9%) of the students did not respond to alerts while in class, while 244 (27.1%) of the respondents responded to alerts while in class.

The findings also revealed the membership of students to certain numbers of social networking sites (Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram etc). It was noted that 124 which represent 13.8% of the total respondents are members of only one social networking sites. As many as 487 (54.1%) are members of two social networking sites, 201 (22.3%) were members of three social networking sites, while 88 (9.8%) were members of more than three social networking sites. Therefore, the findings showed that the students moderately interacted with social media. (Rating: Less than 40% = Low, 40% - 55% = Moderate, Above 55% = High).

Research Question 2: What is the level of students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools? The result was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Teachers Response on Students' Discipline

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Comment
1.	Students usually leave the classroom during lessons	500	2.57	0.865	Moderate
2.	Students come late to school frequently	500	2.74	0.788	Moderate
3.	Students usually engage in truancy	500	2.80	0.711	Moderate
4.	Students engage in bullying in the school	500	2.52	0.961	Moderate
5.	Students sometimes abandon school work to visit social media	500	3.09	0.896	High
6.	Students sometimes engage in insubordination	500	3.02	0.754	High
7.	Students come to school with cell phones	500	2.93	0.945	Moderate
8.	Students engage in examination malpractices	500	2.67	0.874	Moderate
9.	Students sometimes disobey instructions and commands	500	2.92	0.787	Moderate
10.	Students usually leave school premises at will	500	2.93	0.895	Moderate

According to table 2, the findings on teachers' response on the students' discipline revealed that students were moderately involved in disciplinary acts in school as most of the items in Table 2, have moderate responses (Mean < 2 = Low, $3 \leq \text{Mean} \leq 4$ = Moderate, Mean > 4 = High). This implied that the majority of the students were disciplined according to the response of the teachers in the study area. Therefore, the study revealed that the level of students' discipline was moderate.

Research hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools.

Table 3: The relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Rcal	Rtab	Result
Social media-related behaviour	500	2.39	0.856	0.749*	0.065	Sig
Students' discipline	500	2.26	0.872			

* Correlation is significant at (P < 0.05)

Table 3 showed that rCal. (0.749) was greater than rTab. (0.065) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline. This implied that there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline. The relationship between the two variables; social media-related behaviours and students' discipline was high, positive and significant at 0.05 level.

Research hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between social media-related behaviour and students' discipline in Kogi state public secondary schools, situated in rural areas.

Table 4: Relationship between social media-related behaviour and students' discipline in rural areas.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Rcal	Rtab	Result
Social media related behaviour	468	8.5876	2.19	0.265*	0.091	Sig
Students' discipline	468	11.19	3.39			

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 4 shows that r_{Cal} (0.265) is greater than r_{Tab} (0.091) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviour and students' discipline in rural areas. This implies that there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviour and students' discipline in rural areas. The relationship between the two variables was high, positive and significant at 0.05 level.

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that most of the students moderately engaged in one activity or the other on social media. The result showed that 169(18.8%) of the total sample visited social media sites once per day, 389(43.2%) visited it twice per day and 333(37.0%) visited social media sites more than twice per day. This implied that almost all the students visited social media sites every day either while at school or home. Also, 363(40.3%) of the respondents spent 10 minutes, and 411(45.7%) spent more than 10 minutes on each visit. This finding might be due to the perception that children of this age were born into technology inclined environment. The lives of the children of this age could not be separated from global activities. However, it is expected that the knowledge of technology acquired should not be inimical to their educational activities. Spending valuable parts of their time on social media may be preventing the students from engaging in other important activities. This finding is consistent with Roberts et al., (2005), who found out that the behaviours of children and adolescents were highly influenced by their activities on social media. They also noted that time spent online by adolescents increases with age. The study implied that students being adolescents may be spending unnecessarily much time interacting with social media. This finding was corroborated by Fasae and Adegbilero-Iwari (2016) that 70% of respondents engaged in social media activities daily. The result was also buttressed by Clement (2019) that as at third quarter of 2017, 41% of Nigeria population were on Facebook, 41% on WhatsApp, 25% on Instagram, 25% on YouTube, and 24% on Facebook messenger.

The findings on the level of students' discipline revealed that majority of the students were moderately disciplined according to the response of the teachers in the study area. Coming to school with cell phones, abandoning school work to engage in social media, disobeying instructions, leaving the school premises at will, examination malpractice, insubordination to authority, lateness to school and truancy are some of the disciplinary acts that were very noticeable. Female students absconding from home to meet with social media lovers is also an act of gross

indiscipline. This finding was contrary to the belief that the students displayed a high level of indiscipline due to observable manifestations of social media-related behaviour. Social media activities are global phenomena, which many people of this age might perceive as not negatively inclined. They have expected characteristics of children of this age of technology. Earles, Alexander, Johnson, Liverpool and McGhee (2002) noted that how children learn makes the portrayal of violence, sex, drugs, and alcohol through the social media an important contributor to the behaviour of children. In support of this study, Wanjiru (2009) reported that the most indiscipline cases experienced in secondary schools included: drug abuse, stealing, fighting, bullying and sneaking out of school and sexual assault. According to her study, the influencing factors towards these issues were use of drugs, peer pressure from social media group, academic or examination pressure, apathy, poor social background and kind of books and magazines read. In a similar study, Kariungi (2011) revealed that indiscipline among students included, use of uncouth language, rudeness to teachers, absenteeism from schools and drug abuse. The major causes of these behaviours were peer pressure from social media, substance abuse, lack of parental guidance, poor teacher-student relationships and lack of role models. The above studies implied there have been disciplinary issues which were being observed among most of the secondary school students, which may have continued to occur due to exposure to social media.

The study showed that there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline. The reason for this outcome might be because most of the students often interacted with social media. The study revealed that 389 (43.2%) of the respondents visited social media sites twice per day while 333 (37.0%) agreed that they visited social media sites more than two times in a day, either while at school or home. The findings also revealed that 363 (40.3%) of the students spent 10 minutes and 411(45.7%) spent more than 10 minutes on social media sites on each visit. Activities such as chatting, watching video, dating and making friends on social media could greatly influence students' discipline. However, learning experience from social media is a matter of choice. There are lots of positive ideas that could build character and subsequently add value to individual life that are readily available on social media. Ajelabi (2005) agreed that internet chatting was widely utilised by secondary school students both male and female and this greatly influenced their behaviours and discipline. In support of this finding, Mukui (2015) revealed that media use had consequential impact on students' behaviour, either positively or negatively. Furthermore, the report of Badri and Al-Rashedi (2017) also

corroborated this finding that in the process of using social networking, if students encounter any negative thing, it would affect their performance negatively.

The study showed that there was a significant relationship between social media-related behaviours and students' discipline in rural areas. This might be because social media related behaviours seem to be associated with bad behaviours among students in rural areas since there is availability of networks to carry out such activities, which can lead to negative influence on student discipline. It is expected that social media could build up students' interactions and give them ample chance for crossbreeding of ideas, which could be a great advantage to students learning in rural areas. However, students have embraced the negative side of the social media in wrong places and at wrong times. To support this assertion, Morgan, Grahan & Hodges (2012), reiterated that social media activities had impacted negatively on the behaviour and academic achievement of the students.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study established a moderate use of social media by students in Kogi State secondary schools and that their social media behaviour was positive because it was moderate. Relationship between Social media-related behaviours and students' discipline was positive, and the level of students' discipline was moderate. Frequent interaction with social media has not impacted negatively on the behaviours of the students. Furthermore, the study established that social media had impacted positively on the behaviour and discipline of students in rural areas. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made;

- There is a need to monitor the students in their activities on social media. Students should not be indulged in the in spending much of their time on social media. That is, they should be encouraged to use social media at the appropriate time.
- School administrators and teachers need to inform and educate students on the harmful effects of using social media at the wrong time and in visiting the wrong social sites.
- Educational, informative, secured life-enhancing programmes rather than entertainment should be promoted on social media. These will reduce social vices like drug abuse, pre-marital sex and other aggressive behaviours but will promote students' health and well-being.
- Students should not be allowed to come to school with cell phones. Staff members should be mandated to seize cell phones brought to the school by students to avoid distractions on

their studies. That is, a regular and impromptu checking on students should be made to discourage students from coming to school with cell phones.

- Regular enlightenment programmes on issues that relate to social media should be organised by schools to solve students' social media-related problems.

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